

Transitioning from Classroom to Clinical: Lived Experiences of Radiologic Technology Interns during Clinical Internship

¹Shijara Mae D. Encomienda, ²Yezhia Elyz R. Catipon, ³Amiella Glorianne Regalado,
⁴Francis John Reb E. Sales, ⁵Jan Joseph L. Tayam

Calamba Doctors' College

smencomienda@calambadoctorscollege.edu.ph

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Corresponding Email:

smencomienda@calambadoctorscollege.edu.ph

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Abstract. This transcendental phenomenological study aimed to investigate the lived experiences of Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology interns during their clinical internship, with particular emphasis on their transition from the classroom to clinical practice. The five participants for this study were chosen by purposive sampling from the Calamba Doctors' College and interviewed via a semi-structured interview design to collect information on their experiences, challenges, and development during the process of internship. Thematic data analysis was applied in accordance with Clark Moustakas' phenomenology method in order to discover the core elements of the lived experiences of radiologic technology interns. This study established the importance of knowledge from classroom-based lessons regarding patient positioning, anatomy and physiology, radiation protection, and patient care, which were vital aspects that played a critical role in enhancing confidence and competence in the execution of clinical tasks in a safe and accurate manner. Furthermore, it was found that clinical internship was very important because it provided practical learning experiences to radiologic technology interns, making them skilled and knowledgeable about actual healthcare practices. The findings also revealed that this research underscored the significance of patient handling, proper communication, empathy, and professionalism in providing safe, ethical, and high-quality healthcare service to patients. Other qualities such as professional competence, ethical awareness, confidence, accountability, adaptability, and interpersonal skills were also developed through the course of clinical internship, thus playing a huge role in the personal and professional development of radiologic technology interns.

Introduction

Healthcare students' education has always played an important role in the medical field, with a focus on balancing theory and practice. Clinical training in the field of allied health services is one aspect that imparts knowledge to improve professional-level skills. The internship exercise served as a transition between the academic learning environment and the clinical world, which was not always predictable or easy. According to a study conducted by Heydarikhayat, N. et al. (2024), most Radiologic Technology students and other health science interns reported feeling fear of error and stress upon entering a clinical environment. The radiologic technology field was vital because it used different modalities to produce diagnostic images that supported informed medical decisions in the patient's best interest.

The process of transferring students to clinical internships in this area was significant because mistakes in this practice not only affected technical performance but also patient safety. Research indicated that interns usually were not well prepared in safety protocols, which put patients at risk (Toitole, K. K. et al., 2024). Strategies such as flipped classrooms or laboratory-based teaching have been identified to enhance students' clinical preparedness during internships. Moreover, research showed that students' abilities, self-perceived clinical skills, and confidence within a clinical setting were enhanced in simulation-based learning and flipped classrooms compared to traditional lecture-based learning modalities (Agostino et

al., 2024). At Calamba Doctors' College, academic preparation ended at the start of the clinical internship, which would test whether students had mastered the knowledge required in the field. However, the study on the transition from classroom training to clinical work, particularly regarding readiness, confidence, and flexibility among Radiologic Technology interns at the institution, was not well established.

This study sought to fill that gap by exploring the interns' experiences in radiologic technology during their clinical internship. The purpose of this study was to record personal experiences of adaptation, growth, and struggle rather than to base it on a quantitative evaluation of performance. Such research would not only offer meaningful insights into the lived experiences of Radiologic Technology interns but also provide a basis for future research. This research paper concluded by discussing curriculum and ways to improve training programs to ensure better-quality future learning experiences for interns transitioning to a clinical environment.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to conduct an in-depth investigation into the lived experiences of 4th Year Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology interns at Calamba Doctors' College, expecting their responses to reveal the challenges they faced and the unique insights they hold about their day-to-day clinical practice.

Central Question:

What is the essence of the lived experiences of radiologic technology interns who undergo a clinical internship?

Corollary Question:

1. How do the participants describe their experience as they transition from classroom students to radiologic technology interns?
2. What themes may emerge from the testimonies of the participants?

Conceptual Framework

The primary phenomenon studied in this research is the student experience of transitioning from the relatively static classroom environment to a more challenging clinical in radiologic technology education at Calamba Doctors' College. As illustrated in Figure 1, the research paradigm follows the cyclical process aimed at defining the phenomenon's core. The core, as a definition of the problem or key concepts related to the transition, is at the center of the figure. The external, interconnected triangles and arrows show the procedural relationships: transformation of the data collected via Testimonies into Emerging Themes (obstacles and ways to deal with them), which later merge into the Essence of Lived Experiences.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

To create an accurate portrayal of this transition phenomenon, this theoretical framework draws on the transcendental phenomenological framework developed by Edmund Husserl and adopted by Moustakas (1994) for research. It is essential because this approach requires a preliminary stage, Epoché, which involves suspending personal biases and previous assumptions. Since transcendental phenomenology serves as the foundation for the investigation, its conclusions can be drawn solely from participants' perspectives, enabling an objective, purely inductive process for constructing knowledge about professional identity. This theoretical framework directly informs the qualitative methodology by prescribing a systematic, four phase analytical pipeline:

1. Epoché, which creates a baseline level of researcher objectivity before conducting interviews.
2. Phenomenological Reduction helps conduct initial coding and extraction of relevant information from interviews, resulting in the identification of anticipated Emerging Themes.
3. Imaginative Variation assists in the contextual analysis of structural factors influencing the experience of the participants, which may help examine different perspectives.
4. Phenomenological Analysis represents the final stage of synthesis.

By applying this structured methodology, it will offer practical insights into the issues associated with their adaptation and perseverance as well as the processes of professionalization of the students within the field of radiologic technology.

Methodology

Research Design

A transcendental phenomenological design was used for this research, as proposed by Moustakas (1994), to investigate the lived experiences of Radiologic Technology interns as they transition into practice. This design emphasizes participants' perceptions, using epoché to ensure objectivity in the study. In-depth interviews were conducted to gather data, which were analyzed using thematic analysis.

Participants

The participants in this research were five purposively selected fourth-year Radiologic Technology senior interns in the academic year 2025–2026 who had previously completed a clinical internship in hospital settings and were willing to participate and share their experience. Such criteria ensured that the participants had basic knowledge of the clinical setting and were capable of making a contribution informed by the shift between academic learning and clinical practice. Moreover, the researchers ensured that participants' identities were confidential and anonymous. All participants were requested to provide informed consent and to participate willingly.

Instrumentation

The instrument created for this research to gather data was a custom-designed interview guide, aligned with the structure of the statement of the problem. The nine semi-structured questions were asked during the interview, and follow-up questions were posed as needed to understand their experience transitioning from the classroom to a clinical setting.

Data Gathering Procedure

The proposal, approved by the College Administration of Calamba Doctors' College, was sufficient to meet all ethical and institutional requirements, as this study was carried out only upon the appropriate granting of authorization. The researchers gathered five (5) fourth-year Radiologic Technology senior interns, who were notified of the nature and purpose of this study beforehand. One-on-one and semi-structured interview guides were used. Furthermore, the entire interview was audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim with the participant's signed consent. All data gathering processes were conducted in strict adherence to high ethical standards, without infringing on respondents' rights. Moreover, the integrity of the participants was secured by maintaining anonymity through the use of codes, ensuring the confidentiality of participant information, and providing data only to the researchers.

Data Analysis

To explore the lived experiences of Radiologic Technology interns transitioning from the classroom to clinical practice, data were analyzed using Moustakas' (1994) Transcendental Phenomenological approach. This qualitative technique aligned directly with the study's phenomenological design by prioritizing the participants' natural voices through a systematic four-step process: epoche (bracketing personal assumptions), phenomenological reduction (extracting significant statements to form thematic clusters), imaginative variation (exploring underlying structural contexts), and the synthesis of meanings and essences to construct a composite understanding of the shared intern experience. Data organization and thematic coding were conducted manually by the researchers using a systematic, iterative process to ensure a deep, hands-on engagement with the interview transcripts. Within this framework, the analysis directly addressed the research objective of mapping the holistic development and adjustment challenges of the interns while maintaining a reflexive, unbiased, and descriptive account.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers obtained permission from the Dean and the Chief Operating Officer before conducting the study, whilst also following ethical guidelines. Participants were given informed consent forms to ensure the confidentiality of their records and that their participation was voluntary.

All the data that was collected is securely stored and kept private, with no personal information included. Ultimately, the participants were allowed to withdraw anytime if they felt uncomfortable, pointing out that their well-being is also considered in addition to valuing their time and cooperation throughout the study

Results and Discussion

The narratives revealed several recurring patterns in the lived experiences of Radiologic Technology interns as they navigate their transition from classroom learning to clinical practice. Through thematic analysis, nine-major themes emerged that described the essence of the lived experiences of Radiologic Technology interns who undergo a clinical internship.

Theme 1: Integrative Preparation for Clinical Competence in Radiologic Technology

Theme 1, titled "Integrative Preparation for Clinical Competence in Radiologic Technology," reflected how participants described their preparation before entering clinical internship. Their responses highlighted the value of building strong theoretical knowledge, developing mental readiness, and drawing from personal experiences to ease the transition into real clinical settings. These forms of preparation helped them connect what they had learned in the classroom with the realities of hospital practice, making them feel more confident and capable as they began their clinical duties.

The participants, LILY and ROSE, underlined the significance of recognizing theoretical basics, integrating them into clinical practice, and recognizing the realities of the internship. Both interviewees emphasized that a strong theoretical background, with its practical application, was critical in preparing them for the clinical environment. This point of view aligned with the research by Bafaraj and Elkhadir (2022), who reported that students felt challenged to apply the knowledge gained in a clinical setting when it was taught primarily in theory, without proper reinforcement through practice.

Conversely, the participants DAISY and ORCHID focused on the importance of self and mental readiness during the transition from an academic to a clinical setting. This is supported by Ang et al. (2024), who stated that students who received psychological preparation demonstrated significant improvements in confidence, anxiety levels, and preparedness for clinical practice.

Participant DAHLIA, on the other hand, had a different view of clinical practice preparation. DAHLIA's response was based on past life experiences, which helped gain more insight into personal development and wisdom. This perspective aligned with Rutman's (2023) research, which found that an internship experience led to greater self-confidence, flexibility, and a better understanding of professional identity, supporting DAHLIA's point of view.

The participants identified these aspects as important for creating a solid foundation to bridge the gap between academic

learning and clinical practice. Thus, the participants' responses were valuable for understanding the interns' lived experience during this transition.

Theme 2: Enhancing Clinical Competence through Integrated Learning and Practical Experience in Radiologic Technology

According to data collected in Theme 2, titled "Enhancing Clinical Competence through Integrated Learning and Practical Experience in Radiologic Technology," classroom learning played a significant role in students' experience during the classroom clinical internship in the Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology program. This can be attributed to students' emphasis on the relevance of the concepts they learned in the classroom to their real-life experiences.

The stories provided by participant DAISY explicitly showed the connection between classroom ideas and experience in the clinical environment, aligning well with the idea of experiential learning. The literature confirmed this, stating that through experiential learning, students can apply the knowledge they have acquired in the classroom to the real world (Li, Yang, and Jing, 2022).

One more central theme that emerged from the data analysis is the importance of patient care as a main factor in radiologic practice. The students have recognized the importance of patient care through communication with patients of various ages and conditions. The assertions of participants LILY and ORCHID in the interview underscored the importance of patient care in healthcare practice, especially the delivery of quality care through interaction with the patient. This has been substantiated by the fact that patient-centred care is central in the delivery of quality health care and practice (Sharkiya, 2023). Moreover, the other participants, DAHLIA and ROSE, emphasized the importance of good positioning and knowledge as the foundation of radiologic practice. The reason was that positioning has been regarded as a significant competence across imaging modalities, and that knowledge of anatomy and physiology underpinned correct procedures. In this respect, researchers indicate that the concepts of positioning and knowledge are essential for creating high-quality radiographic images. A study by Nyoni et al. (2021) found that positioning was one of the most commonly used techniques in the classroom and in real-world clinical practice.

In general, the theme identified in participants' narratives indicated that classroom-based learning was strongly related to their performance during the clinical internship. The study's findings revealed that participants consistently applied real-life learning experiences in the classroom to patient positioning, handling, and theory.

Theme 3: Challenges and Transitional Hurdles Encountered by Radiologic Technology Interns in the Clinical Setting

Table 3 presents the steps the interns went through as they adapted to working in a clinical setting. The following analysis outlined the overarching themes that defined the transition from academic theory to practical application.

DAISY's experience highlighted the significant gap between classroom practice and patient care. This was in line with Agostino et al. (2024), who said that conventional training did not permit the imitation of self-perceived clinical abilities needed in practice. Similarly, the move towards independence and quicker decision-making was highlighted by participant LILY, who stated that the interns should forget about the spoon-fed classroom environment. This concept aligned with Maniego-Mananghaya (2025), who argued that the Clinical Learning Environment (CLE) was the vital zone in which students transitioned to independent critical inquiry to become professionals.

Besides, another participant, ORCHID, demonstrated professional accountability, stating that punctuality was a way to respect the interdependent team schedule. This was consistent with Aguilar et al. (2023), who had stated that professional socialization and accountability were critical aspects of the internship experience. The challenge of transition was also highlighted by the participant DAHLIA, who noticed the abrupt change between three years of theoretical learning and internship. Lastly, ROSE noted the need for a stronger heart and calmness amid the overwhelming environment in a clinical setting. Thomas et al. (2025) illustrated this by showing that resilience and character strength improved more when navigating problematic interpersonal interactions in the workplace.

The findings indicated that the transition process among Radiologic Technology interns was complex and encompassed Clinical Realism, Professional Autonomy, Accountability, Curricular Readiness, and Psychosocial Intelligence, which were identified as superordinate themes across all interns. This was consistent with the results of Agostino et al. (2024), which indicated that the gap between theoretical training and the unpredictable heterogeneity of real clinical environments was generally enormous among health care students. Moreover, the results revealed that the interns completed the transition

process more quickly in real-life pathology and independent decision-making than in the simulation-controlled classroom.

Theme 4: Experiential Coping and Adjustment in the Clinical Setting

The Theme 4, titled “Experiential Coping and Adjustment in the Clinical Setting,” presented the interns’ coping strategies in response to the challenges encountered during their internship, emphasizing the strategies included ways through which the interns dealt with issues of fear, workload, and clinical pressures.

The narrative of participant DAISY emphasized overcoming fear by acknowledging errors as part of learning, and the importance of asking questions to better adapt to hospital work. Similarly, the need to accept errors and observe experienced practitioners was also highlighted by participant LILY, who noted that interns must have the initiative to ask questions, which corresponded to studies stating that mentorship and guidance were essential in reducing self-doubt and developing confidence during clinical adjustment (Thomas et al., 2025). Furthermore, the focus on handling physical exhaustion by prioritising rest and breaks was reinforced by participant ORCHID. This aligned with the findings of Jeyandrabalan et al. (2022), who emphasised that multiple responsibilities and heavy workloads significantly affected students’ performance; therefore, adequate rest was essential in a clinical setting. Participant DAHLIA also reinforced confidence, adaptability, and determination in effectively handling and responding to difficult situations. This was consistent with studies that utilized resilience and flexibility as essential coping mechanisms in unpredictable clinical environments (Rutman, 2023). In contrast, the gradual adjustment process was described by participant ROSE, acknowledging that it was frightening at first but eventually built confidence through repeated exposure in daily technical routines and imaging modalities.

Their responses indicated that the Radiologic Technology interns faced clinical challenges through experiential coping and adjustment in the clinical setting, which emerged as the superordinate theme across all participants. This reflected a study by Di Mario et al. (2024), wherein healthcare students commonly experienced fear of errors, anxiety, and emotional exhaustion. Moreover, it stated that interns managed workload demands, emotional stress, and difficulties through lived clinical experiences rather than relying solely on theoretical preparation.

Overall, the following subordinate themes aligned with the clinical challenges faced by the interns and were coped with through experiential learning, emotional acceptance, and gradual confidence-building. These strategies were directly discussed to analyse further emotional stress, workload pressures, and the challenges faced with the transition from theory to practice. The thematic table demonstrated the preparation and successful adjustment in the clinical setting, showing that they were fostered by technical and academic competence, effective mentorship, repeated exposure, adequate rest, and resilience.

Theme 5: Transforming Expectations into Radiologic Expertise

The theme 5, titled “Transforming Expectations into Radiologic Expertise,” included the interns’ experiences after the clinical internship, which unveiled the complexity and disparity of the transition from theoretical to practical knowledge. This thematic table captured the range of expectations interns had for this transition.

The non-technical complexity of the role was emphasized in the participant DAISY’s sentiments. The role of the radiologic technologist was not merely to take pictures; it also entailed communicating well with patients, helping them gain confidence and professionalism. This opinion aligned with Estaquio (2022), who found that effective communication was a critical aspect of professionalism, influencing patient care and practical knowledge. However, the experience of participant LILY demonstrated that first perceptions of hospital challenges tend to be surprising and easy.

Participant ORCHID pointed at the large gap between the theory and practice. This highlighted the importance of flexibility and situational learning in good patient handling. Participant DAHLIA’s view was realistic, with expectations for overcoming challenges caused by limited resources. Adequately trained students who also had laboratory-based courses showed greater adaptability to clinical settings (Jeyandrabalan et al., 2022). Lastly, the participant ROSE’s reflection identified gaps in training, focusing on basic skills. The theoretical information was relevant, but the practical experience improved the method of working with patients and emphasized the importance of practical learning. As emphasized by Bhandari et al. (2022), an internship has become a gateway for students into a real healthcare setting, where they can learn and gain new skills that boost their confidence and teach them better practices in the future.

Overall, the accounts of these interns strongly emphasized the transformative impact of clinical internships. Despite variability in expectations and potential challenges, the primary emphasis was on growth, adaptation, and the development of competence through experiential learning. Such considerations underscore the importance of ensuring that the curriculum is designed to meet the demands of the real world, that effective communication skills are developed, and that sufficient resources are provided to facilitate practical training.

Theme 6: Essential Learning and Professional Mastery Obtained by Radiologic Technology Interns during Clinical Internship

Theme 6 identified the main areas of growth and learning reported by the respondents. The following discussion delved into the two main areas of development that emerged during their internship.

The responses indicated that Radiologic Technology interns gained basic knowledge in two significant threads: Professional Identity and Technical Mastery, and Psychosocial Maturity and Emotional Resilience. These two significant threads were the general summaries of all the respondents. This was in line with the clinical learning environment identified by Maniego-Mananghaya (2025) as the backbone of preparedness, in which students were required to combine superior technical competence with the social and interpersonal components of the hospital. The findings also showed a smooth process in which the interns merged the physical element of clinical processes with the mental toughness needed in stressful situations.

Participant DAISY began with the concept of intellectual humility and the realisation that mentorship offered practical advice grounded in the real world rather than what textbooks taught. On the same note, the participant LILY also focused on the shift between passive reading and active doing: knowledge was shaped by immediate experience. This was in line with Agostino et al. (2024), who argued that direct experience enhanced self-rated clinical competence significantly more than classroom instruction. Participant ROSE also noted a change in technique, stating that accurate technique was a professional duty in patient care. On the other hand, participants ORCHID talked about patience. This internal growth was also evident in the DAHLIA's sentiment, which held that having a growth mindset was just a matter of learning to see mistakes as opportunities rather than failures. This was complemented by Heydarikhayat et al. (2024), who indicated that qualitative growth among the interns was facilitated by their proactive approaches to learning about medical errors rather than being scared by them.

All these related concepts fell under the fundamental lessons the interns gained in terms of their technical experience and emotional growth. The theme showed that the ability to do the work (Technical Mastery) during the clinical internship could not be done without the ability to be a professional (Psychosocial Resilience), and the interns were able to conform to the competitive healthcare work environment effectively.

Theme 7: Professional Development in Technical Skills through a Competitive Clinical Environment

Theme 7, titled "Professional Development in Technical Skills through a Competitive Clinical Environment," presented the interns' identified areas for skill improvement based on their internship experience. This theme showed that the skills that needed development, according to the participants, were identified during their internship. These skills included effective communication, technical precision, critical thinking, emotional control, and flexibility within a clinical environment. Also, it showed that the close exposure to the clinical environment led the interns to be more conscious of their gaps in professional readiness. All of these answers helped develop professional skills in technical areas through a competitive clinical environment, as the interns had the opportunity to focus on areas they felt needed refinement while attending to equipment, real patients, and hospital responsibilities.

The need to enhance technical accuracy, communication, critical thinking, and self-confidence was evident in the answers. Participant DAISY noted they needed to improve their communication skills, particularly when caring for patients of different types. The objective was to develop the required speed and precision in the technical handling of the task, since they recognized the need to be more precise and quicker in positioning and manipulating exposure variables, and to improve critical thinking, particularly in special cases. This was in line with Aguilar et al. (2023), who found that exposure in the actual clinical setting would create gaps that students were unaware of at the outset. Participant LILY, who highlighted the value of acquiring technical and technological skills, given the hospital's greater technological orientation. Maniego-Mananghaya (2025) also addressed this, noting that a supportive clinical environment is an important factor that influences interns' confidence and self-competence. Emotional regulation and calmness in any situation were also noted as areas for improvement.

On the other hand, participant ORCHID emphasized the necessity to remain calm but efficient in delivering patient care. This was relatable to the current experience, as Di Mario et al. (2024) demonstrated that these issues are common among learners in the healthcare domain. This stressed that interns learnt that professional competence was not only about technical proficiency, but also about emotional restraint and effectiveness, which they needed to display especially in times of high pressure. Given a broader view of continuous competence development through constant exposure, participant DAHLIA underestimated the desire to enhance it continually. This is consistent with the research by Thomas et al. (2025), which found that the arts of resilience, flexibility, and self-confidence can be mastered through social interaction. Lastly, participant ROSE noted the need to improve the safe management of patients and the implementation of imaging procedures, particularly when it concerns challenging patients, such as those with accidents or trauma. This was one of the expressions of consideration for professional duty, safe patient care, and accountability that needed to be included in clinical adaptation and preparedness, as per Jeyandrabalan et al. (2022).

In general, the theme helped clarify that the improvement ideas the Radiologic Technology interns developed were based on their immediate personal experience. Through interactions with their patients, exposure to a high-tech environment, and exposure to the emotional pressures of a hospital setting, the interns reflected on their own shortcomings. They took the initiative to address deficiencies in their professional competencies. This consequently confirmed their belief that interns base their preparedness levels on experience, learning, emotional adjustment, mentorship, and exposure to the real work environment rather than on academic training.

Theme 8: Cultivating Professionalism and Competence in Radiologic Practice through Clinical Experience

Theme 8, titled “Cultivating Professionalism and Competence in Radiologic Practice through Clinical Experience,” revealed that the clinical internship was a critical and developmental experience that enabled students to move beyond theoretical knowledge toward actual healthcare practice. The results made it clear that the clinical internship was a critical and developmental experience, helping students move beyond the theoretical level to actual healthcare practice. None of the participants differed in their view that the clinical internship was an influential experience that shaped their perceptions of professionalism, ethics, and patient care.

The participant DAISY’s statement highlighted the importance of real clinical experience, as students can develop values and attitudes that they cannot acquire in the classroom. This is supported by Sarkoohi et al. (2024), who showed that clinical internship programs substantially enhanced students’ caring behaviours, commitment to their profession, and critical thinking skills. The case of participant LILY indicated the beneficial impact of the internship on awareness of accountability in radiologic procedures.

According to the participant ORCHID, this experience was a major wake-up call, as students experienced the emotional, interpersonal, and organisational demands of working in a hospital. In line with this, Cui et al. (2025) emphasized that students are exposed to the real-life clinical setting, which demonstrates to them the multidimensional aspects of healthcare work, emotional and professional challenges. By collaborating with technologists, nurses, helpers, and other healthcare personnel, the students learned to respect the teamwork process and understand the profession’s dynamics. Similarly, participant DAHLIA referred to the very real world outside of school as an internship. Lastly, participant ROSE discovered that the ability to study how to handle patients with various medical conditions only reinforced the importance of good communication skills and ethical values in a clinical environment.

The research studies clearly confirmed that the clinical internship was not only a course requirement but also a competency-based, compassionate, and ethically grounded learning foundation, preparing students to become competent, patient-centred radiologic technologists.

Theme 9: Integrating Skills and Knowledge in Radiologic Practice

Theme 9: Integrating Skills and Knowledge in Radiologic Practice explored the abundance of wisdom and tips offered by interns to those about to enter clinical internship. The participants’ stories highlighted the holistic approach required to succeed in a clinical internship.

The participant feedback from DAISY highlighted the importance of goal-setting and a positive attitude in boosting motivation. It is also a key aspect of embracing mistakes and restructuring skills as recommended by DAISY. Similarly,

participant DAHLIA highlighted the importance of viewing mistakes as opportunities for growth. This compromise between making errors and patient safety was the cornerstone of practice. Hendy et al. (2025) believe that such psychological resources as self-efficacy, the belief in his/her ability to succeed, can be cultivated, which may help to improve the performance of a professional.

Participant LILY focused on the practical aspects of navigating the clinical environment, emphasizing the importance of protocol awareness and active learning. This recommendation focused on the significance of professional growth in the healthcare field by prioritising the knowledge of protocol, active learning, and patient-centred care. On the other hand, participant ORCHID highlighted the role of pleasure and relaxation in improving learning. In addition, tasks and peer work received special attention, which helped improve efficiency and, in turn, created a more favorable learning environment. Supporting this, Maniego-Mananghaya (2025) examined the impact of the clinical learning environment on students' professionalism. Lastly, participant ROSE recommended the value of preliminary knowledge and preparation before entering a clinical internship.

To sum it all up, the recommendations from these interns provided a good roadmap for future radiologic technology interns. These perceptions provided a comprehensive approach to success in this critical journey every student must take to become a licensed professional, emphasizing the importance of goal-setting, attitude, protocol knowledge, active learning, teamwork, and preparation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that learning, professional development, and adaptation were associated elements of the lived experiences of Radiologic Technology interns during their clinical internship. The findings revealed the participants' experiences, challenges, and adaptations through themes such as integrative preparation of clinical competency, development of clinical competence involving both integrated learning and practice, problems and transitional barrier, coping and adjustment in the field or experience, turning expectations into practice of radiology, learning and professional mastery, nurturing of professionalism and competence, and integrating skills and knowledge into clinical practice. Overall, the findings showed that despite the difficulties the interns experienced in adapting to the clinical setting, the learning process during their internship program better prepared them and made them highly competent in a real-world professional setting.

The study also offers practical implications for improving the seamless transition of Radiologic Technology students from the classroom to the clinical environment. Administration should introduce structured pre-clinical orientation programs to ensure quality training in a clinical setting, good supervision, and efficient learning. Regular assessments may help clinical instructors effectively monitor and support interns' progress, and facilitate and oversee collaboration between academic institutions and clinical training sites to ensure alignment of objectives and clinical competencies. Officials may also enhance the quality of internship programs by updating existing memorandum orders to ensure alignment with current clinical standards. Institutions and training facilities may revise the curriculum to enhance the practicality of classroom learning and its application in a clinical setting, where a conducive learning atmosphere allows interns to practically apply the knowledge and skills they have gained in the classroom. Furthermore, future research should examine various institutions to better understand the factors that determine clinical competence, professional development, and internship preparedness.

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Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.